

ISic1414

I.Sicily inscription 1414

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Soluntum

Place of origin (modern)

Solunto

Provenance

agora portico, in situ

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Solunto, Area Archeologica e
Antiquarium di Solunto

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR136726

1. □:in latere sinistro□
2. ἐπὶ ἱεροθύτα Φίλωνος Ἄπ [ολλωνίου]
3. Ἄριστω[ν] Ἄ[πολλωνίου]υ τὸν π [ατέρα]
4. Ἀπολλώνιον Ἄ[ρίστωνος ἀμ]φιπ[ολή]σα [ντα]
5. Διὶ Ὀλυμπίωι καὶ θεοῖς πᾶσι
- 6.
7. □:in latere dextro□
8. ἐπὶ ἱεροθύτα Φίλω[νος] Ἄρίστωνος
9. Ἀπολλώνιος καὶ Φίλων] καὶ Ἄρίστων Ἄρίστωνος
10. τὸν πατέρα Ἄριστ[ωνα Ἀ]πολλωνίου
11. ἀμφιπολήσαντα Διὶ Ὀλυμπίωι καὶ θεοῖς πᾶσι

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644965

EDR 136726

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 46.1242c2

Tusa, V. 1963. L'anfipolia a Solunto. *Kokalos*. 9: 185-194. At no.2

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